

SCIENTIFIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING MEAT PRODUCTIVITY IN HISAR LAMBS

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Abstract. *This article examines the scientific principles underpinning the improvement of meat productivity in Hisar lambs through supplementary feeding. It analyzes the growth and development dynamics of lambs involved in the experiment and explores the relationship between biologically active substances in blood serum and meat productivity.*

Keywords: *productivity, energy, biological potential, protein, hematological parameters, carbohydrates, proteins, hormones, protein, vitamins, macro-and microelements, erythrocytes, leukocytes, hemoglobin.*

НАУЧНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ МЯСНОЙ ПРОДУКТИВНОСТИ ГИССАРСКИХ ЯГНЯТ

Аннотация. *В статье исследуется взаимосвязь между дополнительным кормлением, ростом и развитием гиссарских ягнят, а также содержанием биологически активных веществ в сыворотке крови и их влиянием на мясную продуктивность. Выявлены ключевые факторы, способствующие увеличению выхода мяса у гиссарских овец.*

Ключевые слова: *продуктивность, энергия, биологический потенциал, протеин, гематологические показатели, углеводы, белки, гормоны, витамины, макро- и микроэлементы, эритроциты, лейкоциты, гемоглобин.*

Introduction. A critical factor in the growth and development of animals is the intensity of biochemical processes, which perform essential functions within the tissues and organs of all growing organisms. The scientific foundations for enhancing meat productivity in livestock production lie in leveraging the biological characteristics of Hisar sheep.

By utilizing aged, non-productive Karakul ewes, non-viable rams, and lambs with substandard pelts that do not meet market demands, the volume of meat production can be increased through supplementary feeding alongside grazing. During the grazing process, factors such as pasture capacity, weather conditions, and pasture yield are taken into account [1,5].

For the sustainable development of Karakul sheep farming, it is considered effective to preserve and proliferate only those breeds capable of producing high-quality, competitive products for global markets. Consequently, creating opportunities for improved meat productivity in Karakul sheep farming relies on the judicious use of natural pastures and supplementary feeding.

In arid regions, exploiting the biological potential of livestock bred for meat production yields favorable results. Ensuring the supply and availability of high-quality meat products to the population remains one of the pressing issues of today [4,6,7].

All nutrients present in food products can conditionally be categorized into three groups: those that meet the organism's energy requirements, those involved in cell and tissue construction, and those regulating metabolic processes.

The composition of feed encompasses all three categories of nutrients (the first group includes carbohydrates and fats, the second group consists of proteins and hormones, and the third group comprises micro- and macroelements, vitamins, and enzymes) [2,5].

In Karakul sheep farming, lambs with pelts of suboptimal quality that fail to meet market standards are primarily raised for meat production. Early fattening of such animals proves to be economically beneficial for farms. Keeping lambs with inferior pelts incurs additional expenses for feeding, veterinary services, and grazing.

Moreover, as pasture capacity increases, the degradation and decline of pasture ecosystems become inevitable. While the costs associated with their maintenance rise, the quality of meat products also improves. However, such circumstances can lead to significant economic losses for the farm [3,8].

Research Methodology. For the purposes of this study, average-weight Hisar sheep, to be raised in various ecological regions, were selected. The quantitative indicators of biologically active substances in the blood composition, as well as the milk productivity of the sheep, were examined using universally accepted biological methods. The obtained results were subjected to biometric analysis according to the method of N.A. Plokhinsky.

Conclusion/Recommendations. The growth and development of young animals are entirely dependent on hematological indicators within the organism. Furthermore, the growth and development of the organism are closely related to external environmental factors, including the conditions for protection from adverse influences, nutrition, feed preparation, and the biological value of the feed.

In livestock farming, meat products are primarily derived as follows: lambs slaughtered at 1-3 days of age are considered "barrow meat," lambs slaughtered at 4–4.5 months of age are classified as "suckling meat," and lambs that are one year old are categorized as "yearling meat."

Sheep that exceed one year of age are classified as "mutton." In livestock farming, one of the most effective methods for increasing meat productivity in sheep is supplementary feeding.

To study the impact of the nutrition factor on meat productivity, experimental and control groups were selected based on age, physiological state, and the degree of fatness, following the principle of similarity in Karakul sheep.

Animals in the experimental group were provided with a supplementary high-protein diet, while the control group was fed with a standard farm diet.

Supplementary feeding of the animals in the experiment

Indicators	Barley	Wheat germ	Bran	Total	Per 1 kg
Quantity, kg	37,0	13,0	50,0	100,0	1,0
Feed unit	0,40	0,18	0,37	95,0	0,95
Metabolizable energy, MJ	3,92	1,86	4,77	1055	10,55
Dry matter, g	297,5	127,5	425	8500	850
Crude protein, g	39,5	10,44	76,5	1265	126,5
Digestible protein, g	29,7	8,85	56	9450	94,5
Vitamins, g	0,17	0,15	1,3	162	1,62
Macro and microelements, g	1,75	0,51	5,45	771	7,71

In countries with well-developed Karakul sheep farming, such as Australia, New Zealand, Bulgaria, and England, meat production is carried out by fattening 6 to 8-month-old lambs.

The biological potential of fattening Karakul lambs with low-quality wool has been utilized in limited societies, such as the "Bobotog-Suri" project, where experiments were conducted. Both the experimental and control groups were kept under identical grazing conditions.

The experimental group received additional feeding. During the first 10 days, the lambs were fed with their mothers once a day.

Subsequently, the amount of feed was increased by 20% and given twice a day, separated from their mothers.

The growth and development indicators of both groups of lambs were monitored at the ages of 4–4.5 months and 8.0 months.

The growth and development of the lambs in the experiment, in terms of meat productivity indicators, kg.

Lamb group	n	Growth and development					
		At 2,5 months of age		At 4-4,5 months of age		At 8 months of age, slaughter yield	
		M ± m	C _v	M ± m	C _v	M ± m	C _v
Experiment	8	14,38±0,58	5,25	24,3±0,47**	7,12	16,54±0,45**	5,32
Control	8	14,29±0,32	5,59	21,4±0,31	8,03	14,38±0,87	5,89

Note: < 0,01**

The lambs in both the experimental and control groups were raised under identical pasture conditions, with lambs chosen to be analogous in terms of live weight and color.

As shown in Table 6.6.1.3, there were no significant changes in live weight at the age of 2-2.5 months for the lambs in both the experimental and control groups.

This result is statistically significant (P < 0.001). After supplementary feeding starting at 4.0-4.5 months, the lambs in the experimental group exhibited an increase in live weight, reaching 24.3 kg, which is 18.7% higher than the 21.4 kg (16.0%) observed in the control group.

During slaughter, the meat yield of the lambs in the control group was 14.38 kg (14.8%), while in the experimental group, it was 16.54 kg (12.4%). The average difference was found to be 13.4%.

The growth rate potential during the feeding process was more pronounced in the experimental group, indicating a higher performance. This difference was statistically significant.

When analyzing the correlation between the biological active substances in the blood plasma, such as AST, total protein, erythrocytes, leukocytes, and hemoglobin, and meat productivity, it was observed that in the experimental group, where additional feeding was provided, there was a noticeable connection between the biological active substances in the blood plasma and meat productivity.

Starting from the age of 2 months up to the slaughter time at 8 months, it was found that with increasing age, the levels of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) in the blood plasma slightly increased, and in comparison to the control group, the levels in the experimental group were significantly higher. Starting from the age of 2.5 months, AST levels in the experimental group were, on average, 2.0 units higher. The levels of total proteins in the experimental group were also found to be significantly higher, ranging from 6.3 to 6.7 units.

This suggests that in the experimental group, the increased activity of metabolic processes is indicated by the enzymes.

Furthermore, animals in the experimental group, who were additionally fed, showed higher levels of total proteins in the blood throughout all months of the study.

The relationship between the biologically active substances in the blood serum and meat productivity upon supplementary feeding (n=8).

Biologically active substances	Growth and development							
	At 2,5 months age		At 4-4,5 months age		At 6-6,5 months age		when slaughtered at 8 months of age	
	M ± m	C _v	M ± m	C _v	M ± m	C _v	M ± m	C _v
Experimental group								
Aspartate Aminotransferase	42,8 ± 11,5	4,29	43,3 ± 12,8	5,28	43,7 ± 11,7	5,25	43,8 ± 12,4	6,25
Total protein	71,5±2,1	2,33	72,5± 3,4	2,08	73,2 ± 1,81	3,02	73,5±2,1	2,28
Erythrocytes	9,85 ± 8,4	1,51	10,57 ± 10,3	2,42	10,81 ± 11,2	2,93	11,27 ± 11,4	1,84
Leukocytes	7,25 ± 0,24	0,21	7,28 ± 0,84	0,89	7,47 ± 0,59	0,54	7,85 ± 0,984	0,29
Hemoglobin	11,5 ± 3,12	2,21	11,84 ± 2,56	3,40	12,8 ± 2,87	2,07	12,4 ± 3,54	3,02
Control group								
Aspartate Aminotransferase	40,8 ± 10,7	3,51	41,7 ± 11,7	6,87	41,5 ± 10,6	4,52	41,3 ± 12,2	5,52
Total protein	65,2 ± 3,2	1,28	66,8 ± 2,5	1,29	68,5 ± 3,1	2,20	68,9 ± 3,3	3,82
Erythrocytes	8,54 ± 7,8	0,98	8,59 ± 5,4	1,48	8,85 ± 4,5	3,39	8,98 ± 3,7	1,48
Leukocytes	7,53 ± 1,4	0,36	7,81 ± 0,58	0,37	7,87 ± 0,89	0,45	7,69 ± 1,87	0,29
Hemoglobin	9,89 ± 2,87	3,84	10,8 ± 2,69	2,48	10,2 ± 1,98	2,65	10,7 ± 2,08	3,47

Experimental group. Note: p<0,01**

Conclusion: The animals with higher levels of total proteins in their blood exhibited greater growth and fattening, as confirmed in the experiments. No significant changes were found in the levels of the formed elements of the blood, including erythrocytes, leukocytes, and hemoglobin.

However, in the experimental animals, where the variation in the formed elements was more significant, higher meat productivity indicators and economic efficiency were observed and analyzed.

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